

Title: Analysis of Prevention Techniques against DDoS and SQL Injection Attack in Network and Cloud Environment.

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Abstract:

Besides other benefits, one of the main goals within cloud computing is to achieve scalability by continuously decreasing and increasing the number of networking resources such as virtual machines, databases, networks, storages and more, to match resource demands. In the other hand, it also allows organizations to reduce cost through enabled services that are designed to manage performances and storages. Cloud computing is defined on the concept of the internet, this means such networks are not immune to downtime infiltrated DDoS and SQL attacks, but also it can be compromised by attacks from outside. As the name suggests, Denial of service. This, including SQL attack's Common Vulnerability and Exposures (CVE) base score, are usually rated high with critical severity classification, suggesting that its implications can be very damaging on the network. Shielding the network from such attacks requires maximum defensive methodologies, not just for protecting but also for mitigating purposes. Achieving such results means implementing processes that are relevant for detecting, containing, and mitigating DDoS and SQL attacks on the network. However, this may not be easy as some common challenges in detecting DDoS and SQL attacks have been blamed on unreliable and inconsistent false positive signals coming from different IDS and IPS tools. To get deeper into this we can divert the attention of this research, not only on how to track such alert sources, using selected IDS and IPS tools such that may include hardware or software respectively, through which we can validate its results in a comparative manner for the sake of differentiating false positives, against false negatives. Alternatively, we could achieve this purpose through educational learning methods and tools.

Keywords: [Cloud Security](#), [DDoS Mitigation](#), [SQL Injection Attack \(SQLIA\)](#), [Web Application Firewall \(WAF\)](#), [Input Sanitization](#), [Parameterized Queries](#), [Rate Limiting](#), [Network Security](#), [Traffic Analysis](#), and [Intrusion Detection System \(IDS\)](#)

1.Introduction:

The migration of local data centers is fast moving to the cloud, leaving traditional computer network models behind, that are more of proprietary base systems design. Such networks are defined as hardware and software specifications, that are or could only be managed under a single domain name or enterprise. When compared to cloud computing implementation, that are subjected to the concept of the internet and software defined methodologies. This model provides grounds for remote management, allowing traffic monitoring and engineering. The fact that cloud computing relies completely on the internet for data transportation, exposes the network to various attack vectors, allowing digital offenders to manipulate their ways through one means or the other, including SQL injections and DDoS attacks to penetrate illegally and steal network resources. In recent years, cyber vulnerability has grown so rapidly, with significant damage recorded such as the 2013 Target Corporation and Yahoo SQL Injections on United State based companies. (Garg, A. (2023). *SQL Injection: The Cyber Attack Hiding in Your Database.*). Various forms of SQL Injections e.g. In-Band SQLi (Classis), Inferential SQLi (Blind) and Out-of-Band SQLi and DDoS attacks including the Application layer, HTTP Flood, Protocol, and Volumetric attacks are most famous orchestrated on both private and public domain networks. So how to keep cloud computing safe from online criminals remains a serious concern. Judging from network related perimeters, achieving scalability, flexibility, accessibility, reliability, and security has become an important point of discussion within networking arena, as software-based networks within cloud infrastructures are constantly faced with unreliable setbacks including system generated errors like false positive feedback, malware, Trojan and IP flooding. To better understand DDoS and SQL attacks, we shall carry out self-network analysis from a virtualized environment, with a view to detecting, analyzing and preventing true alerts using some selected free Intrusions, detection and prevention (IPS) and Intrusion detection system (IDS) tools such as Suricata, SolarWinds, Damn Vulnerability Web Application and more. Before we forge ahead with investigation, let's review DDoS and SQL injections and possible vulnerable means through which these attacks can penetrate a network.

2.0 Distributed Denial of Services Attacks.

These classified malicious cyber-attacks are aimed at temporarily forcing cloud distributed resources offline with the purpose of denying legitimate users access to relevant directories from servers to other cloud base data centers. Botnet, sometimes referred to as Zombie army, are typical DDoS attacks that can hijack internet-connected or networked devices, from a remote location with the help of malware applications, leaving the device or network owner unaware of its present or even activities being carried on within. Most of which often use the dark web and Tor browsers to initiate such connections. It's not exaggerating to mention that the frequency of DDoS attack occurrences on cloud networks in recent times is becoming alarming with multiple

severity ratings from low to high. Such attacks are happening using different forms of attack methodologies on targeted vectors within private and enterprise networks including Application, Presentation, Session, Transport, Network, Datalinks, and Physical levels. DDoS attacks can be sub-classified based on the Open System Interconnection (OSI) model's layer where it's originally initiated. Such attacks on organizational and private networks are not slowing down, rather a survey shows that there has been a high increase in the spread bridging from governmental, healthcare to private institutions respectively according to the US department of health and human services (hhs.gov). Renowned for flooding the victim's network with echo ping request messages, also known as ICMP (Internet Control Message Protocol). DDoS attacks are usually merged with three divisible parties which we can further review their means of operations including sources.

2.1 The application level, also known as level 7, attackers can flood the network with congested traffic filled with fake content ICMP messages, once users accept this messages, attackers will automatically gain control of the user's device using it to spread same messages across the whole network, eventually forcing legitimate users to logout of the network due to unavailability of the network connection and resources cause by congested traffic. Attacks at the application level can be orchestrated via HTTP, or expensive search Application Programming Interface, since it's the only level within the OSI model where end users are connected, known as the user interface (UI) for consuming network or cloud computing resources. Application attacks are very sophisticated and considered more than just a volumetric type, that are built for vulnerable exploitation within applications and services, operating using the same application. These attacks usually occur over internet request traffic within applications routed transactions.

2.2 Volumetric attacks, normally grouped under infrastructure layer attack, there are no strangers to network insecurity since it's often detected due to the consistency in the frequency of occurrences. Attackers usually target the network from layer 3 or 4 of the OSI model, with the aim of flooding heavy traffic to the server and eventually forcing the network to be not responsive, resulting in packet loss, resource unavailability. Attacks on layers 3 or 4 are responsible for traffic interruption since both network layers do not only define how traffic is routed but also are responsible for the protocol that routes data from one device to the other. Regular examples include synchronized (SYN) floods and User Datagram Packet floods as well. Volumetric attacks cause high impact traffic bottlenecks; hence they capitalize on UDP, DNS, and TCP transport control protocols including application traffic servers to penetrate and brimming the network with choked data traffic. Some network devices that can be affected by this attack include servers, routers and more. It's never challenging identifying volumetric attacks; however, mitigating may require flow telemetry, web application firewall, rate limiting, etc.

2.3 Protocol Attacks, also called state-exhaustion, are contrary to volumetric attack and are aimed at transporting channels. Protocol attacks on the other hand are designed to target network resources on the servers and communications; this may include hardware or software connecting websites and web servers. An example would be a firewall, or a load balancer. Attacks are usually operated when hackers attempting to consume web pages or server resources illegally, will manipulate their ways by designing fake protocol requests to interrupt communication channels between domain's internal and external links which are usually built around the firewall. Hackers can penetrate a network using a Smurf DDoS attack. If successful, they can gain access and control the domain's Internet Control Messages Protocol which is critical to the organizations as it holds vital information such as Spoof IP address, leading to IP broadcast, that are used for data transmitting within the network.

3.0 Structured Query Language (SQL) Injection Attacks.

SQL Injections remain one of the most critical cyber insecurities that have been used to attack computer networks both in the past and in modern computing eras. According to Kaspersky, SQL injections, notoriously known for web application vulnerability, have been at the center of digital insecurity back in the 1990s when the internet started making waves around computer networks. With this explainer, we can find out more. SQL or SQLi Injection, is a vulnerable act that permits digital offenders to rely on a piece of structured query language (SQL) code, to make changes on a database by granting him/herself permission to a private device or a network's critical information. Such attacks in many cases are usually carried out on applications or web pages that are supported with SQL databases. To successfully execute an SQL attack on a network, a hacker is required to understand the structured query language (SQL) used in defining access, editing and storing data. understanding the SQL structure, gives the attacker an idea of what and how certain activities can be query on the SQL server. Let's review some SQL injections.

3.1 Error-based SQLi injection, this occurs when an attacker attempts an operation on an SQL database, a displayed error message may give an attacker an ideal solution to resolving the error/s. As a result, an attacker can eventually obtain access to the database. In most cases, system engineers and technicians rely on message errors for troubleshooting steps in resolving incidents.

3.2 Time-based SQLi injection, in this case, attackers operate with caution while conducting such activities by having to wait for feedback from the saver, after special requests are initiated to force the saver to go on sleep or pause service for a given period. During this period, hackers can vulnerably penetrate the server from outside the network. Time-based SQL injections are suitable when application configuration means

to withstand error messages does not meet the intended mitigation purpose subject to SQL injection attacks on the network.

3.3 Boolean-Based SQL, attackers depend on the feedback from the SQL server or application, based on false or positive results. This can be very slow, especially when data is huge or on large database.

4.0 Detecting DDoS and SQL Injections attacks

Having understood exactly what DDoS and SQL injections attacks are, may underline the impacted area within cloud computing, however, it does not define any processes or means in which such attacks can be exposed. So, if we were to forge ahead in search of mitigating and controlling solutions for cloud network-based resource attacks, it will be necessary to first understand how these attacks can be detected.

4.1 Detecting DDoS attacks, sometimes it requires extra effort in identifying DDoS attacks, this is because a deeper networking understanding of *data quality*, and *transportation*, may be essential in separating original data from compromised packets while in transit. Data transportation and security is subjected to traffic behavior, allowing network administrators to capitalize on the abnormality from the traffic or rely on machine learning categorization methods, in extracting bad data packages from good ones. Frameworks for detecting DDoS attacks on a network are built around two components as indicated.

I. Deep Packet Inspection (DPI): the process is also known as Packet sniffing; it permits network administrators to analyze data or packets as it transits through checkpoints on the network. DPI analysis data from various perspectives including headers and packages. Which is different from the traditional stateful packet inspection that only checks the device details, port number, source and destination IP addresses. DPI offers a more detailed investigation mechanism for packet filtering, constant packet-sniffing framework, and most importantly, detects hidden threats around data transportation including illegal cyber acts of data exfiltration, content modification policies, malware detection and many more. In-line monitoring tools including software and hardware devices are usually attached directly to the network and are designed to constantly filter malicious activities.

II. Out-of-Band Traffic Monitoring. When compared to In-line tools, out-of-Band monitoring tools, on the contrary, examine copies of the network traffic while making available detailed information about traffic patterns and irregularities, in a way that does not trigger technical issues on the network performance. This process is an optional suitable security solution for designing and implementing variable access methodologies for administering services on devices that are connected to the network infrastructure and can be done without connecting to the corporate LAN network. Out-

of-Band software or hardware solutions are greatly used for monitoring purposes and network troubleshooting benefits.

4.2 Detecting SQL Injections Attacks. Identifying and mitigating SQL injections can be done in many ways, depending on the processes, tools and protection frameworks implemented which can be subjected to the intended security goals. Security policies configuration can be defined and applied, based on hardware and software applicable. This could vary based on certain tools embedded, (e.g.) in certain scenarios, we can identify, contain and mitigate SQL injections attacks on the network with the help of Intrusion Prevention systems (IPS). In this regard, an IPS software or device, to be secured, must be visible and exposed within the application traffic. For example, applications that are encrypted with HTTPS protocols without limitation within an average network device would withstand an IPS traffic monitoring perimeter's capability in identifying SQL injections attacks on the network.

I. SolarWinds's Security Event Manager (SEM), is a security information and event management (SIEM) System, designed with additional features to collect and analyze security-linked information on the network. Smart features on this tool can automatically identify suspicious activities, send notification and receive automatic responses linked to suspicious attacks according to network monitoring defined policies and rules applied on the configuration. Security Event Manager (SEM) can be installed as an application on a local device, a standalone device or administered in a cloud-based environment, but only as an intrusion detection systems (IDS) type. This is because it only serves for the purpose of monitoring and detecting malicious acts, such as those violating security configurations and settings applied on the network. An example of an alert that can be identified by SEM IDS tools, includes DNS poisoning, Malformed information packets, Christmas tree scan and more.

II. Inferential SQLi Injection, this does not occur easily as time concern is an issue with this injection type. Nevertheless, it's just another SQL malicious attack that can occur on an application server. This attack does not rely on data transfer within the application interface as compared to other attacks, this makes it difficult for the attacker to gain visible results on the in-band. This is why this is classified as a blind SQL injection attack. An attacker may however be able to rebuild the database structure by routing payloads and monitoring application's web feedback alongside the database server's behavioral output. Inferential SQL Injection are categories on two sections known as Blind-Boolean-based SQL and Blind-Time Based SQL.

5.0 literature review.

The new era of computer resources sharing has not only approached and embraced the internet as a moving forward solution, but unfortunately it has also initiated the end of

proprietary computer networks since many organizations have already moved to the cloud, and lots more have also embarked on discontinuing on-premises networking infrastructures. This seems good to hear but it has not positioned internet connected devices or their users on the right location on the map, rather it has also given birth to a new era of cyber-crimes with notable network offences being DDoS and SQL injection attacks. To confront this attacks, many efforts against DDoS and SQL injections attacks have been made and tested by different organizations operating in various domain of businesses from corporate enterprise networks to institutions of learning around the world, some of which have produced and documented workable solutions that can be found on various journals including online publications like Amazon web services, the national library of medicine (NIH), Springer-Open Journal of big Data, IEEE Xplore digital library, the national Crime Agency UK and many more. Some information sourced from digital libraries and achieved for Analysis of Prevention Techniques against DDoS and SQL Injection Attack on Network and Cloud Environment have engaged various solutions including the use of machine learning and data mining. On a related note, survey shows that researchers are now directing more attention in investigating digital attacks on cloud computing, which is not a surprise because traditional computer networks were designed on proprietary defined methodologies, much of which did not require advance protection tools like firewalls, IPS and IDS for protecting its gateway IP addresses, or such domain boundaries were not mapped against the internet. For that reason, computer networks were much safer since resource distribution was not subjected to the internet contrary to the new era's cloud computing. However, as change is constant in information communication technology (ICT), sometimes it can be demanded for high priority reasons that require rapid implementation, not just for better service but also security concerns. This has prompted researchers to embark on developing new solutions or attributing new ideals to already existing ones to help combat DDoS and SQL injections attacks on cloud computing networks.

The aim of this research is not only to merge already existing solutions in a comparative scale, that includes analyzing fault positive and accuracy predictions and related cyber insecurities, but also to contribute to the development of solutions by extracting meaningful results from predicted alerts generated from network monitoring tools for cloud computing.

We could start by acknowledging efforts already made by cyber security solution providers including researchers, security hardware and software developers whose innovations are creating safe passages not just for storing and accessing data, but also for transportation within cloud networks. For example, according to the *ieeexplore* library, *Alkasassbeh et AL*, a professor of Computer Science at Princess Sumaya University for Technology in Jordan, has benefited from data collected from separated network layers on SIDDoS and HTTP flood, to successfully defend and prevented

DDoS and SQL injection attacks on the network. (Alkasassbeh, Mouhammd et al). Other recorded technology includes the *Seven Based on the Adaptive Selected verification, that was developed by Dantas Y et AL*, whose creations allow network administrators to fight DDoS attacks at the network layer of the OSI model. Though, the tool may be deemed failure due to notable recorded analytics generated within according to the *ieeeeexplorelibrary*. The tool was designed to operate on the concept of the notion of a state around the application layer, however findings show that DDoS attacks at the application layer do not function on the notion of the state. The article further elaborated that the tool has failed against attacks such as HTTP Post Flooding because of the excessive number of reflectors used to transport payloads.

We wish to contribute towards the Analysis of Prevention Techniques against DDoS and SQL Injection Attacks in Network and Cloud Environment, by making use of some selected free IDS and IPS tools available online, not just in generating results, but also to rely on analyses gathered within, in developing solutions for detecting and mitigating those attacks on the network.

6.0 Scanning, Identifying, and Mitigating SQL Injections attacks.

Moving ahead, we shall present a combined diagram with two virtualized computing networks, projecting not just theoretical ideals but also technical concepts which are set up on two separate operating systems, namely Khali Linux and Ubuntu respectively. These outlines analytical outputs from different tools which are installed on the virtual networks. The tools are not just digital security software but are also freely designed for educational and training purposes useful for achieving intended goals within cyber security. We can gain enormous experience with these tools, firstly, by conducting a vulnerable penetration attack test assignment while acting as the **Red Team**, from outside on a selected network device, in view of obtaining unwanted access to resources. Secondly, we can act as the **Blue Team**, in performing a network scan to determine the attack vector where hackers vulnerable gain access to penetrate the network. Finally, we shall proceed in identifying the threats with the aim of developing mitigation strategies for containing related attacks.

6.1 Network Scan with OWASP Zap. The first step is to perform either an active or a passive network scan from a Kali Linux virtualized environment using OWASP free software, with the aim of identifying vulnerabilities on the system that could eventually be used as attack vectors against the network. The scanning process is, however, not be done directly on the virtual system, rather than a free installed education training software known as Danm Vulnerable Web App (DVWA).

6.2 A passive Scanning Mode. on a Khali Linux based network device using OWASP from DVWA can be beneficial for the following reasons.

- Firstly, to highlight an educational training need, by allowing network admins or trainers to aid users test web application security skills and tools.
- Secondly for HTTP proxy's request analysis and responses in view of identifying potentials security glitches, hence DVWA is a PHP/MySQL web application that is intentionally designed with cyber vulnerabilities within, to allow security professionals gain practical knowledge by identifying and exploiting them according to Edge Nexus.

6.3 Active Scanning Mode. Although this involves more technical engagement in implementing the process, it's usually considered more effective and reliable by security administrators in obtaining multiple results which are relevant to finding cyber vulnerabilities on the network. Benefits including the following. Active scanning will be our preferred scanning mode for this project.

I. Active scanning gathers data from real-time network responses while passive scanning focuses on network traffic and logs.

II. Active scanning enables and makes changes within the sent to applications, by sending requests that surface vulnerabilities one cannot obtain through passive scanning. The purpose of scanning is aimed at targeting and obtaining SQL injections information's on the DVWA application installed on Ubuntu computer within the VMware. To meet the requirements, we have successfully installed OWASP Zap 2.15 application on the local Khali VMware, with mandated Fuzz DB files add-ins relevant not just for enabling SQL payload, but also useful for initiating manual scan especially on an active mode. See Zap default scan menu.

We shall manually perform an active scan using the OWASP Zap, with the aim of finding any available SQL vulnerabilities. The exercise is designed to be carried out as a penetration test where the **Khali Linux's Red team** will target the **Ubuntu Machine's Blue Team**. From the Ubuntu device we login to the DVWA application from the web browser using the DVWA application local host URL from the address bar, which is as follows: <https://localhost/DVWA/Security.php>, using administrative credentials which allow us to set the security level to medium on the application as seen on the attached file.

From the host Virtual machine operating on Khali Linux with an IP address of 172.16.72.131, through OWASP Zap scanning tool, we also set the tool to attacking mode and entered the IP address of the targeted machine on Ubuntu operating system with an IP address of 172.16.72.129 within the same virtualized environment. Since we are specifically searching for SQL injections, we need to configure the Fuzzer Location on OWASP scanning tool, so we can add SQL injections as payload before attacking the Ubuntu virtual machine remotely from the Khali Virtual machine. Please see screen shorts

From the OWASP application, we have just launched an attack from Khali Linux machine's address: 172.16.72.131 on Ubuntu virtual Machine's IP address: 172.16.72.129, as displayed below.

7.0 Identifying, Analyzing, Classifying Threats Impacts Ratings While Suggesting Mitigations Strategies for Containment.

According to the scan results, five alerts are flagged under history which we will not only look at their impacts, threat or risk levels ratings, but we shall also suggest mitigation strategies through for preventing such SQL attacks against the network. We can further classify threat levels in colorful ratings to determine not just the impact and risk but also the possibilities of occurrences at which such attacks can take place on the network. Finally, we can also look at their perimeters as well.

I. Content Security policy (CSP) Header Not Set (23).

CSP is an additional security level that has been included to aid in detecting and mitigating some forms of attacks on the network such as Cross Site Scripting (XSS) and data injection attacks. Such attacks provide meaningful mechanisms for data theft, site defacement or distribution of Malware.

Risk levels: Medium

Ratings: High

Color: Orange

Perimeters: N/A

Mitigation strategies: Making sure that the web server, application server, load balancer, firewall and routers are configured to allow Content-Security-Policy header.

II. Missing Anti-Clickjacking Header.

Recent websites are protected by certain security measures known as Content-Security-Policy and X-Frame-Options HTTP Headers. An alert generated by these errors means that the website or browser has not been secured using this very technology. Which simply means that the website is exposed to vulnerabilities and can be hacked easily by cyber offenders. Clickjacking is a digital manipulation technique that allows hackers to trick their victims by clicking alternatives resources instead of the intended needs, while browsing the web.

Risk Levels: Medium

Ratings: Medium

Color: Blue

Perimeter: X-Frame-Option.

Mitigation Strategies: To maintain modern protection levels requirement for securing web browsers and HPP headers, it is important to configure at least one is set to allow all web pages returned by the site or application. If you desire the page to be framed only by pages on your own server such as making them part of the FRAMESET.

III. Server Leaks Version information via “Server” HTTP Response Header Field 24.

Hackers will easily find and exploit security vulnerabilities in web applications if servers leak version information are exposed from the HTTP response header field. Some useful information that is leaked from this location include information detailing technology and software platform which the server operates on. Scan reviews the header exposing the software that the server uses to handle requests. This is just sufficient information required by attackers to start spying and collecting relevant information which can then be used to decide an attack nature to penetrate the network.

Risk levels: low

Ratings: High

Color: Red

Perimeter: N/A

Mitigation strategies: The risk level for web and application threats may be rated low, however its impact on the network could be severe if successfully hacked by cyber criminals. This is not to say applications, websites or enterprise network owners should remain in fear, but rather take advantage of implementing some security frameworks listed below to defend such attacks. Fix may include:

- Enabling the mod_headers module by performing a2enmod headers.

- ❑ Open the Apache httpd.conf file.
- ❑ Remove the X-powered-By header if it exists.
- ❑ Restart Apache by running `systemctl restart apache2`.

(NB) a security concern to be noted is that HTTP headers allow the client and server at the same time to share information as part of the HTTP protocols, which makes application less secure.

IV. X-Content-Type-Options Header Missing

It's not unusual to find error/s indicating X-Content-Type-Options Header Missing. Such errors occur when applications servers have been vulnerably attacked by hackers who take advantage of gaining access to the network through an application, in the event where traffic is not being monitor over the server via the Anti-Multipurpose Internet Mail Extension Sniffing framework, (Anti-MIME-Sniffing). This is supposed to be enabled within the '*X-Content-Type-Options*' header response. If this option is not enabled, it therefore permits hackers to carry out content-type sniffing on the application from outside the network. A typical example of such attack is Cross Site Scripting (XSS).

Risk levels: low

Ratings: Medium

Color: Blue

Perimeter: X-Content-Type-Option.

Mitigation strategies: As indicated earlier, ramifications to such attacks are as the result of failing to turn on Content-Type Header options within the application and we server, which set the X-Content-Type-Options to Nosniff for all web pages, to prevent hackers from using the browser to sniff or execute unwanted MINE type. The solution is to enable options.

V. Information Disclosure – Suspicious comments.

Cyber-attacks take place in various forms, an attack vector including software, hardware, a piece of information, end user, or gaining unauthorized physical access to certain premises defines security bridges which are very useful tools hackers may rely on to penetrate a network. Disclosing certain information about the network such as system data, usernames, access keys, encryption keys, source code, configuration files, internal application details, and user’s personal information, could be very meaningful for a hacker to obtain useful information that can be rely upon to invade a network.

Risk level: Informational

Ratings: Medium

Color: Blue

Perimeter: N/A

Mitigation strategies: Removing ever comment with feedback details that could aid a kicker and make changes within the underline issues referring to.

8.0 Scanning, Identifying, and Mitigating DOS and DDoS attacks.

As indicated within this project, we can use various intrusion detection tools for analyzing network traffic, capturing and displaying real-time content details on how data is routed and secured from one IP address to the other. Picking an IDS tool all depends on the goals the user intends to achieve. In this scenario we have opted to use

Wireshark network IDS tool, not just for obtaining network log analytics for enhance security improvements, but also for educational purposes as mandated for this research project. It's also important to note that practical processes implanted within our virtualized environment for training benefits are like those within enterprise and private organizational network setup.

8.1 Wireshark Network Analyzer: Wireshark is an open-source network analyzer pre-installed on Khali Linux operated devices but can also be installed easily on most common operating systems. The tool is designed to operate as an IDS, with inbuilt features that permit network administrators to carry out multiple network tasks, including the following.

- ❑ **Network traffic monitor:** in view of identifying vulnerabilities and threats including Dos and DDoS attacks.
- ❑ **Network performance troubleshooting** has taken control to resolve issues occurring within the network traffic.
- ❑ **Packet captured** by validating network traffic into human readable or consumable data type.
- ❑ **Real-time analysis:** this provides updated details of the network status, providing quick information on current network activities.
- ❑ **Network filtering features:** this makes it much easier for admins to direct attention on specific traffic transactions, allowing analysis to be target and recorded easily.
- ❑ **Features capabilities.** The graphic user interface means the tool can be used from GUI which makes it easy for beginners while experts can rely on the command prompt interface.
- ❑ **Security analysis:** detect and analyze unwanted network threats.
- ❑ **Protocols analysis:** capable of reviewing the inside movement of each protocol while data is on transit.
- ❑ **Multiple view support.** Wireshark offers both graphic and I/O analytics views from granular level, allowing multiple options to capture data in real-time analysis.
- ❑ **Multiple protocols support** example, TCP, UDP, ICMP, ARP, HTTP, HTTP2, FTP, and WebSocket

8.2 Identifying Secure Network Connection with Wireshark. To establish a secure connection between two or more devices, in any networking scenario from LAN to WAN, the setup should be defined on a process known as *A handshake*. This could be a TLS, Three-way, or a mobile device charger handshake. The purpose is basically aim at

ensuring that every node or device within that network, can communicate effectively and secured, while allowing transmitting protocols to reliably route data across from one end to the other during transit, by making sure any distraction such as attempt to slow traffic, modify data, or any form of security threats, are detected, and mitigated. In a TLS handshake, this can be done by allowing network devices to agree on a master shared secret information in which more than one key can be used for securing data's integrity and confidentiality by guaranteeing it availability in every session establishment. See TLS 3-way Handshake.

The question we can ask is *why a handshake?* The role of a three-way handshake in a TCP protocol connection using HTTP or HTTPS is highly mandated for securing such connections. For example, if a client attempts to access resources from the server over any of these protocols, firstly a packet is sent which is known as **synchronization (SYN)**. Secondly, an acknowledgment of security configurations must be, or is done by the server which is known as **SYN-ACK packet**, to create a secure connection between the transport protocol. Finally, the connection can be identified as secured and enabled for data to be exchanged known as **Data Transfer**. This means that data can only be transferred between those network devices that are involved in that security configuration or have passed the security requirements through synchronization acknowledgment.

8.3 Identifying Unsecured Network Connections with Wireshark.

Therefore, the purpose of this clarification is to differentiate how Internet Control Messages Protocol (ICMP) flood, which is a typical Denial-of-service DDoS or DDoS attack, can initiate unsecured connections with the Central Server without any acknowledgment or authenticating principles, to overwhelm the server with hundreds or even thousands of echo messages which usually end up by forcing legitimate users out of the network, given attackers control to infiltrate the network with threats such as

Spoofing, Syn flood, Ping of death, Smurf attack, ICMP packet size, etc. These forms of attacks are aimed at bridge any forms of security measures subject to any vulnerable threat vector that are available, and can be used to launch attack/s. See below how a DDoS attack can be initiated from multiple IP addresses to a central server.

8.4 Internet Control Messages Protocol: was originally created for the purpose of testing existing connection between two network IP addresses, with the aim of assessing the amount of time it would require for those echo messages to travel from one end to the other. As time goes on the tool has been developed to improve network securing through monitoring internet's health condition and resources attack's ability. However, internet hackers have found comfort in this, capitalizing on it, using same ICMP packages from the original source IP address or using spoofing as an alternative's solution, to generate high volume echo-request packets such as ping request, ICMP request and data packets. A notable point within gathering huge volume of data while transit is that it can also serve hacker's interest in many ways including attributing cyber risk on the network, hence hackers can also consume high available bandwidth on the destination IP address or device making it unavailable within the network for legitimate consumers.

8.5 Identifying Dos or DDoS attacks with Wireshark. Using Wireshark, we can track Dos and DDoS attacks on the network using either manual or conversational mode by analyzing the PCAP files generated within the tool. A PCAP file is responsible for recording and storing copies of every packet data transmitted on the network. If log analytics results from the PCAP files indicate a high-volume traffic or data from a

particular or multiple source IP address/s, especially unidentified sources, are directed to the server or a particular node on the network, this could therefore suggest irregularities linking to suspected Dos or DDoS attack on the network. Such traffic in many cases lead to ICMP flood, Syn flood etc. attack. Let's attempt a practical scan using Wireshark to verify findings. As mentioned earlier, Wireshark allows us to detect attacks using either Auto or Conversational mode, which can be displayed for analysis in a graphic or I/O views.

In a conversation mode we want to see irregular high-volume DDoS or Dos traffic attacks coming from unknown sources destined to a particular host with no response. Firstly, there are two data viewing options we need to differentiate when analyzing packets from Wireshark security tool known as the Captured and Display Filters.

8.6 Captured Filter: This is used for filtering when capturing data or packets. It can also be used to reduce the amount of data that is captured and included in the raw captured packets. Filtering options can include IP address or device name, gateway host identity, connection port numbers or type, connectivity (e.g.) WIFI or Lan. Soon as we launched Wireshark, from the capture menu we selected the host WIFI or Ethernet IP address as the network path we want to scan as seen below.

Immediately we select capture, Wireshark starts scanning. We can decide to prolong scanning or stop and move to the display mode for analysis.

We aim to detect a denial-of-service attack, by analyzing data from Wireshark display filters. As indicated previously, such attacks can be captured in a non-respond high traffic package directed at a specific destination IP address, if existing data shows 0 to 2400 packet/second are sent with no reply. Now let's analyze data in conversation views. From the statistics tab, we select conversation. We can also customize settings under protocols, to suit not just our needs but also views as seen below.

8.7 Display Filter: This is the main area of the tool that allows users to gain control over the display option of a selected packet. You can choose which packet to analyze and compare transmitting protocols against a selected filtered value from the capture menu. Filtering also allows features for statistics generation and data listing colorization.

Now to filter display, we can list by protocols, selecting (e.g.) UDP we can see below directed traffic to the IP address: 192.168.8.110.

Conversation Settings

- Network protocol
- Absolute start time
- Limit to display filter

Copy

Follow Stream...

Graph...

Protocol

- Bluetooth
- BPP
- DCCP
- Ethernet
- FC
- FDDI
- IEEE 802.11
- IEEE 802.15.4
- IPv4
- IPv6
- JXTA
- LTP
- MPTCP
- NCP
- openSAFETY
- RDP
- SCTP
- TCP
- Token-Ring

Filter list for specific type

Help

Close

Address A	Port A	Address B	Port B	Packets	Bytes	Stream ID	Packets A → B	Bytes A → B	Packets B → A	Bytes B → A	Rel Start	Duration	Bits/s A → B	Bits/s B → A
192.168.8.110	52564	2.16.162.71	443	38	17 kB	1201	18	11 kB	20	6 kB	938.574071	1.0970	83 kbps	40 kbps
192.168.8.110	56706	2.16.162.71	443	19	7 kB	862	8	3 kB	11	4 kB	883.49162	30.1327	838 bits/s	1000 bits/s
192.168.8.110	64074	2.16.162.71	443	903	908 kB	416	154	20 kB	749	888 kB	342.860992	7.8718	20 kbps	925 kbps
192.168.8.110	60232	2.16.162.71	443	75	23 kB	313	33	11 kB	42	14 kB	338.032518	3.9289	21 kbps	28 kbps
192.168.8.110	53034	2.16.162.71	443	21	8 kB	559	9	4 kB	12	4 kB	403.066638	30.1027	1183 bits/s	1018 bits/s
192.168.8.110	54985	2.16.162.71	443	39	19 kB	420	18	9 kB	21	10 kB	343.226112	0.5502	124 kbps	145 kbps
192.168.8.110	56311	2.16.162.71	443	20	7 kB	656	8	3 kB	12	4 kB	463.101105	30.0688	642 bits/s	1015 bits/s
192.168.8.110	60853	2.16.162.71	443	152	106 kB	416	55	10 kB	97	97 kB	342.998080	0.4511	170 kbps	1714 kbps
192.168.8.110	61654	2.16.162.71	443	34	17 kB	349	15	6 kB	19	11 kB	340.167151	0.3113	156 kbps	281 kbps
192.168.8.110	123	17.253.110.99	123	2	180 bytes	1393	1	90 bytes	1	90 bytes	1108.848878	0.4591	1568 bits/s	1568 bits/s
192.168.8.110	66216	17.253.110.99	123	2	180 bytes	179	1	90 bytes	1	90 bytes	200.490702	0.5293	1360 bits/s	1360 bits/s
192.168.8.110	123	17.253.110.125	123	4	360 bytes	2090	2	180 bytes	2	180 bytes	2008.861713	0.0371	38 kbps	38 kbps
192.168.8.110	51122	17.253.110.125	123	2	180 bytes	185	1	90 bytes	1	90 bytes	201.051738	0.0303	23 kbps	23 kbps
192.168.8.110	54300	17.253.110.125	123	2	180 bytes	180	1	90 bytes	1	90 bytes	201.028239	0.0224	32 kbps	32 kbps
192.168.8.110	123	17.253.110.253	123	6	540 bytes	1384	3	270 bytes	3	270 bytes	1109.312579	899.5486	2 bits/s	2 bits/s
192.168.8.110	55283	35.227.252.103	443	56	28 kB	901	30	17 kB	26	11 kB	884.151970	1.4215	93 kbps	61 kbps
192.168.8.110	64608	35.227.252.103	443	41	22 kB	1095	21	15 kB	20	8 kB	923.128263	1.6258	72 kbps	38 kbps
192.168.8.110	53693	41.73.41.78	443	62,805	73 MB	493	6,102	632 kB	56,503	73 MB	342.273405	533.3864	9473 bits/s	1088 kbps
192.168.8.110	58691	41.73.54.77	443	21	13 kB	500	10	5 kB	11	7 kB	348.927216	0.1281	311 kbps	464 kbps
192.168.8.110	52560	41.73.55.35	443	39	23 kB	1672	16	5 kB	23	18 kB	1437.174110	0.2057	204 kbps	691 kbps
192.168.8.110	64112	41.73.55.35	443	34	20 kB	1671	14	5 kB	20	16 kB	1437.164214	0.1525	267 kbps	776 kbps
192.168.8.110	5971	52.98.20.162	443	37	22 kB	704	18	6 kB	19	15 kB	638.489722	0.4760	108 kbps	256 kbps
192.168.8.110	53071	52.98.20.162	443	56	32 kB	962	26	8 kB	30	24 kB	340.779037	0.7779	82 kbps	244 kbps
192.168.8.110	53301	64.233.184.157	443	117	94 kB	378	48	18 kB	69	76 kB	889.128485	0.4923	284 kbps	1235 kbps
192.168.8.110	65094	64.233.184.157	443	120	94 kB	1101	48	17 kB	72	76 kB	928.888094	0.7204	194 kbps	848 kbps
192.168.8.110	5971	66.1021.1.84	443	29	20 kB	1568	13	6 kB	16	15 kB	1345.331764	0.6579	184 kbps	184 kbps
192.168.8.110	63976	66.1021.1.84	443	28	13 kB	132	13	7 kB	15	7 kB	141.331803	0.6570	82 kbps	79 kbps
192.168.8.110	63084	74.125.133.155	443	27	10 kB	943	13	6 kB	14	10 kB	886.738485	0.8730	53 kbps	89 kbps
192.168.8.110	49345	108.177.15.84	443	27	13 kB	2051	12	7 kB	15	6 kB	1947.300691	0.8794	78 kbps	75 kbps
192.168.8.110	49472	142.251.47.66	443	28	18 kB	1174	14	8 kB	14	10 kB	1211.982518	1.5207	184 kbps	184 kbps
192.168.8.110	51852	142.251.47.66	443	27	16 kB	1172	13	7 kB	14	10 kB	933.535424	0.4253	128 kbps	179 kbps
192.168.8.110	53338	142.251.47.66	443	28	18 kB	1168	14	8 kB	14	10 kB	933.488091	0.4345	151 kbps	176 kbps
192.168.8.110	55846	142.251.47.66	443	28	18 kB	1164	14	8 kB	14	10 kB	933.449120	0.4710	139 kbps	162 kbps
192.168.8.110	56861	142.251.47.66	443	28	18 kB	1177	14	8 kB	14	10 kB	933.707874	0.4647	141 kbps	164 kbps
192.168.8.110	57324	142.251.47.66	443	34	21 kB	1181	16	10 kB	18	11 kB	933.775410	0.4843	160 kbps	184 kbps
192.168.8.110	57408	142.251.47.66	443	28	18 kB	1188	14	8 kB	14	10 kB	933.867899	0.4648	141 kbps	164 kbps
192.168.8.110	57605	142.251.47.66	443	28	18 kB	1196	14	8 kB	14	10 kB	933.977816	0.4343	154 kbps	164 kbps
192.168.8.110	58763	142.251.47.66	443	34	21 kB	1192	16	10 kB	18	11 kB	933.935504	0.4773	162 kbps	184 kbps
192.168.8.110	61830	142.251.47.66	443	26	16 kB	1184	12	7 kB	14	10 kB	933.815810	0.4848	111 kbps	157 kbps
192.168.8.110	62971	142.251.47.66	443	19	14 kB	1335	9	4 kB	10	9 kB	1072.353722	0.2388	149 kbps	303 kbps
192.168.8.110	63638	142.251.47.66	443	25	16 kB	2071	13	6 kB	12	10 kB	897.756868	0.3968	151 kbps	181 kbps
192.168.8.110	63938	142.251.47.66	443	25	14 kB	1867	12	6 kB	13	8 kB	1068.220270	0.3969	128 kbps	151 kbps
192.168.8.110	50826	142.251.47.70	443	26	15 kB	1030	13	5 kB	13	10 kB	891.096083	0.4293	100 kbps	179 kbps
192.168.8.110	52838	142.251.47.70	443	26	15 kB	1151	13	5 kB	13	10 kB	928.934224	0.4393	98 kbps	174 kbps
192.168.8.110	54291	142.251.47.70	443	26	15 kB	1142	13	5 kB	13	10 kB	928.767816	0.4312	99 kbps	178 kbps
192.168.8.110	55396	142.251.47.70	443	54	24 kB	1102	24	11 kB	30	12 kB	927.112560	1.8468	48 kbps	53 kbps
192.168.8.110	56581	142.251.47.70	443	27	16 kB	1110	14	7 kB	13	10 kB	927.600779	0.4725	113 kbps	162 kbps
192.168.8.110	60051	142.251.47.70	443	27	16 kB	1116	14	7 kB	13	10 kB	927.688193	0.4490	118 kbps	171 kbps
192.168.8.110	60388	142.251.47.70	443	28	14 kB	985	15	11 kB	28	13 kB	898.448208	1.6831	54 kbps	66 kbps
192.168.8.110	61178	142.251.47.70	443	26	15 kB	1127	13	5 kB	13	10 kB	928.575843	0.4439	97 kbps	173 kbps

If we list protocols by TCP, we can see traffic to same IP address.

Conversation Settings

- Network protocol
- Absolute start time
- Limit to display filter

Copy

Follow Stream...

Graph...

Protocol

- Bluetooth
- BPP
- DCCP
- Ethernet
- FC
- FDDI
- IEEE 802.11
- IEEE 802.15.4
- IPv4
- IPv6
- JXTA
- LTP
- MPTCP
- NCP
- openSAFETY
- RDP
- SCTP
- TCP
- Token-Ring

Filter list for specific type

Help

Close

Address A	Port A	Address B	Port B	Packets	Bytes	Stream ID	Packets A → B	Bytes A → B	Packets B → A	Bytes B → A	Rel Start	Duration	Bits/s A → B	Bits/s B → A
192.168.8.110	62885	2.16.162.71	443	19	4 kB	198	11	3 kB	8	1 kB	342.923907	3.7826	6154 bits/s	13 kbps
192.168.8.110	62980	2.16.162.71	443	22	8 kB	213	11	3 kB	11	5 kB	343.316499	3.3651	6033 bits/s	13 kbps
192.168.8.110	63025	2.16.162.71	443	24	10 kB	215	11	3 kB	13	5 kB	343.316735	3.3649	6186 bits/s	13 kbps
192.168.8.110	63030	2.16.162.71	443	36	10 kB	267	19	8 kB	17	2 kB	348.604153	3.1014	21 kbps	21 kbps
192.168.8.110	63031	2.16.162.71	443	20	4 kB	268	11	3 kB	9	1 kB	348.854050	2.8622	8206 bits/s	17 kbps
192.168.8.110	62981	2.16.162.71	443	26	8 kB	180	12	3 kB	14	6 kB	339.957006	1.8210	11 kbps	11 kbps
192.168.8.110	62982	2.16.162.71	443	26	8 kB	181	12	3 kB	14	6 kB	340.456960	1.3748	15 kbps	15 kbps
192.168.8.110	62949	2.16.162.71	443	143	85 kB	101	60	12 kB	83	72 kB	342.609221	4.0766	24 kbps	24 kbps
192.168.8.110	62966	2.16.162.71	443	19	4 kB	199	11	3 kB	8	1 kB	342.924070	3.7824	6123 bits/s	13 kbps
192.168.8.110	62950	2.16.162.180	80	10	1 kB	182	6	826 bytes	4	542 bytes	342.813544	4.0669	1624 bits/s	16 kbps
192.168.8.110	62961	2.16.162.180	80	6	416 bytes	193	4	276 bytes	2	140 bytes	342.833067	3.8374	576 bits/s	5 kbps
192.168.8.110	63246	2.17.195.138	443	32	7 kB	516	16	5 kB	16	2 kB	952.307870	3.9696	10 kbps	10 kbps
192.168.8.110	63279	2.17.195.138	443	32	7 kB	576	16	5 kB	16	2 kB	1248.321834	3.0123	13 kbps	13 kbps
192.168.8.110	63326	2.17.195.138	443	33	7 kB	728	16	5 kB	17	2 kB	1848.348247	2.2700	17 kbps	17 kbps
192.168.8.110	62853	2.17.195.186	443	31	7 kB	33	16	5 kB	16	2 kB	48.304093	2.8220	14 kbps	14 kbps
192.168.8.110	62853	2.17.195.186	443	31	7 kB	33	16	5 kB	16	2 kB	168.312492	2.8166	14 kbps	14 kbps
192.168.8.110	62864	2.17.195.186	443	32	7 kB	91	16	5 kB	16	2 kB	288.338906	2.8321	14 kbps	14 kbps
192.168.8.110	63055	2.17.195.186	443	31	7 kB	299	16	5 kB	15	2 kB	408.357314	2.8332	14 kbps	14 kbps
192.168.8.110	63096	2.17.195.186	443	32	7 kB	349	16	5 kB	16	2 kB	708.363424	2.8854	14 kbps	14 kbps
192.168.8.110	63309	2.17.195.186	443	31	7 kB	663	16	5 kB	15	2 kB	1648.523565	2.0368	19 kbps	19 kbps
192.168.8.110	58673	2.21.98.208	443	24	14 kB	89	10	2 kB	14	12 kB	284.214910	1.8795	9129 bits/s	9129 bits/s
192.168.8.110	59059	2.21.98.217	443	24	14 kB	743	10	2 kB	14	12 kB	1940.44			

9.0 Mitigating Strategies against DoS and DDoS attacks:

Intruders can always find illegally access to cloud-based network resources if any vulnerable loopholes present the opportunity to be exploited. Threats exploits are constantly availing themselves in various means and within cloud networks, allowing SQL injections, Dos and DDoS attacks to take high priority in applications, web browsers and other options to steal data. Having provided some solutions for SQL Injections, let's further review mitigations strategies for DDoS and Dos attacks. We seek summaries, instead of extended elaboration on these strategies.

- Analyzing and monitoring traffic over the network.
- Implement firewalls for web applications. (WAF)
- Implement Botnet mitigating services.
- Develop a DDoS response plan for your network.
- Redirect traffic to reduce further spread on the network.
- Hardware configuration, including load balancers for content delivery.
- Develop maximum cloud security methodologies.
- Network partitioning or submitting to eliminate the spread.
- Further security practices are listed at 10.0 ahead.

10.0 Security practices against SQL and DDoS Cyber threats

Shielding cloud networks from hackers remains a global challenge as they have also resolved to use SQL Injections and DDoS attack methodologies as unwanted access to steal cloud resources. Cloud networks are subjected to the internet and are prone to hacking, however practicing a good security attitude will not only give hackers a tough task in penetrating into a domain but will also boost the security of that network. Our research identified multiple vulnerabilities on the network that can easily be compromised by intruders to access resources. In addition to mitigation strategies suggested as solutions for containing those SQL Injections fuzzed as payload during the scan, we also recommend that cloud network operators develop defensive systems against traditional cloud intrusions, based on their security needs, using the following practices according to Microsoft, but this is not limited to tools including IDS and IPS.

- Deciding on the right cloud service provider.
- Knowing your security requirements or what to protect.
- Define strong authentication mechanisms.
- Use various encrypting methods.
- Protect cloud resources within users' location.
- Define the use of access control management.
- Constantly monitor cloud activities to determine security requirements.
- Implement strong authentications for APIs.
- Adopt constant employees' cyber training awareness.
- Practice Zero trust principles.
- Use firewalls, IDS and IPS.
- Network isolation will eliminate the device affected from the network.

11.0. Conclusion.

Although our research is aimed on fulfilling educational goals, however it's also important to say this has been carried out from a similar virtualized computing network environment just as it would be on any enterprise network scenario, where the purpose was not just about analysis of prevention techniques against DDoS and SQL Injection attacks, but we could use the same practices to successfully determined mitigating strategies against those identified vulnerabilities recorded from scan results affecting cloud based network resources. On a similar note, cloud computing is designed to run on virtualized technology using the internet as the backbone, which makes sense for organizations to save cost on flexibility and portability, hence tens of virtual machines

can be chained just on one infrastructure alone as system management units, which enormously limit hardware needs. This may facilitate easy network resource accessibility, which is not limited to any geographic boundaries, but cyber insecurity challenges. Maintaining a cloud network is not just about the smooth operations in delivering resources from servers to clients, but also making sure data is safe and may not be intercepted or modified by hackers while in transit. This requires implementing relevant mechanisms including hardware and software like IDS/IPS but also adhering to organizational security policies and practices such as those we have listed on the table of content 10.0 to fight SQL injections and DDoS attacks and further related threats.

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